

Climate negotiations: Uncertainty about climate thresholds

Review of an Experimental and a Mathematical Approach

Seminar Environmental Economics

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Abstract

Barrett and Dannenbergs game theoretic experiment, and Barretts game theoretic mathematical model, state that threshold uncertainty is the core issue of climate change policy making. This review challenges this statement by reviewing the game theoretic assumptions and conclusions made by Barret, and Barrett and Dannenberg, namely player homogeneity, fundamental scientific uncertainty, and the game theoretic classification of climate change not being a prisoners dilemma.

1 Introduction

Coping with climate change struggles with political stalemate and inefficient contributions to climate policy goals. We will review two articles ([Barrett and Dannenberg \(2012\)](#), [Barrett \(2013\)](#)) that locate the problem at threshold uncertainty, the main issue being that uncertainty of thresholds negatively impacts decision making. To model the impacts on decision making, Barrett, and Barrett and Dannenberg, use game theory. The problem of climate change is often described as an instance of a prisoners dilemma game, a situation where the players strategies result in a sub-optimal state, due to incentives for defection away from the common, Pareto-optimal solution. Barrett argues, that different games (assurance game, asymmetric dilemma) are being played under threshold uncertainty.

In the context of climate change, the threshold in question is at the first glance a temperature threshold. At a second glance, and one causal link back, the threshold in question is the level of concentrations of greenhouse gases (GHG), measured in parts per million by volume (ppm) of CO₂ equivalents. The 5th IPCC report states e.g. a complete loss of the Greenland ice sheet at a threshold somewhere between 1°C and 4°C global mean warming. There exists scientific uncertainty about the tolerable level of concentration, and the threshold is located in the range from 350 ppmv to 550 ppmv. The UNFCCC committed to a 2° warming target, which should be met in order to avoid possibly

catastrophic events. Barrett and Dannenberg show in their experiment, and Barrett argues in his mathematical model, that under uncertainty of thresholds, policy and decision making become significantly disturbed, and cooperation necessary to achieve common goals becomes nearly impossible. The breakdown of cooperation leads to an erosion of emission reduction targets and to unfulfilled pledges to mitigation and adaptation funds.

In the following we will review the experimental setup used by [Barrett and Dannenberg \(2012\)](#) and mathematical modeling used by [Barrett \(2013\)](#) to analyze threshold uncertainty, and discuss the implications of the results for policy making. The methodology used here consists of a document analysis and methodological review. The document analysis will summarize the main arguments, the main method applied, and the main result of each paper reviewed. In a more detailed step of methodological review we will discuss the characteristics of the general approach, how methods were applied, and whether the underlying assumptions are legitimately chosen for the problem of climate change. We aim to answer the question whether threshold uncertainty is the right perspective to take in climate change policy making.

2 Review of approaches of Barrett and Dannenberg

2.1 Main Arguments

In [Barrett and Dannenberg \(2012\)](#) the argument is established, that collective action fails not because an impact is uncertain, but because of uncertainty at which point or threshold the impact occurs. This may be the case when net benefits (avoided damages minus avoidance costs) are not high, or not guaranteed. In climate change this may refer to mitigation costs and avoided climate damages. Additionally there is an incentive to deviate from the commonly better solution, because individual contributions matter little and the better solution may be reached anyway through contributions of the rest of the group, while oneself may reap the additional benefits of defection.

In [Barrett \(2013\)](#) Barrett builds on the experimental results and establishes a mathematical model involving a discontinuous benefit function. The main argument is, that the collective action problem changes from cooperation game to coordination game once threshold is known. At this point the payout matrix changes, and nature becomes the external enforcer of a treaty, and a political contract or social institution is no longer needed. When the net benefit of avoiding a threshold is high, cooperative behavior is a Nash equilibrium. On the other side of the threshold lies another Nash equilibrium, which is Pareto inferior. The Pareto inferior Nash equilibrium comes into being because one country alone is not able to avoid catastrophe. The distinction made between a cooperation game and a coordination game is that cooperation needs to be enforced in some way, since there are incentives for defection from the collectively optimal solution.

2.2 Methodology used by Barrett and Dannenberg

Barrett and Dannenberg (2012) devised an experiment to show the influence of uncertainty on strategic behaviour in a collective action context. Their experimental setup tested the behaviour in four environments (certainty, impact uncertainty, threshold uncertainty, impact and threshold uncertainty). Follow-up questionnaires were used to test the participants understanding of the game, and to ask about their reasoning and decision making.

The experiment conducted involved 400 students randomly arranged into groups of ten. The experimental setup promised a participant 20€ for participation. The payout was influenced by the course of the game and especially the performance of each group. Depending on the outcome of the game, players could lose a certain amount of money (*impact*) if the group as a whole did not reach a common goal (*threshold*). While contributions were costly, there existed an incentive to contribute in order to avoid losses through impacts.

Figure 1: The x-axis shows the actual contributions of each player, the y-axis shows the pledges. (Barrett and Dannenberg (2012), p. 17374)

In the *certainty* scenarios, impact was set to 15€, and the threshold was set to 150. In the *uncertainty* scenarios the impact level ranged from 10 to 20 in a uniform distribution, with an expected value of 15; the threshold level ranged from 100 to 200 in a uniform distribution, with an expected value of 150. One major obstacle was to convey the role of uncertainty in the game. This was achieved with a spinning wheel, visualizing the randomness in setting impact level and thresholds. Control questions handed out together with numerical

examples tested the participants understanding of uncertainty within the game.

The game itself was played in a neutral framing, without any mention of climate change or other collective action problems. No communication between players was allowed. The game was played in four stages: Propose, pledge, contribute, and payoff determination. In the first stage, each player proposed a sum the group as a whole should aim for. In the second stage, each player made a pledge indicating the amount he or she was willing to contribute. In the third stage, each player contributed an amount of own discretion to the group. In each stage the players individual decisions were made covertly, and then revealed to the group at the same time. In the last stage the payouts were directly revealed. In the case of uncertainties, impact and/or threshold were determined by the spinning wheel. Payouts were therefore not known before the last stage. The results of the plays is shown in figure 1. In the case of certainty and impact uncertainty, they are clustered around the threshold value of 15. In the case of threshold uncertainty and impact and threshold uncertainty (with an expected threshold value of 15), pledges vary widely, and in most cases contributions do not match pledges.

The mathematical model constructed in (Barrett, 2013) consists of a game situation where the payout is determined by a benefit function which is discontinuous at a threshold. There exist at most two Nash equilibria on either side of the threshold. Discontinuous in this case means that on one side of the threshold, where the impact is comparably high, catastrophe avoidance is collectively optimal. On the other side of the threshold, where impact is comparably low, avoiding catastrophe is inefficient. Then there exists a band in between, where catastrophe avoidance is collectively optimal but cannot be reached as a Nash equilibrium. Should impact and threshold fall into this band, cooperation becomes necessary to achieve the collectively optimal solution.

2.3 Results

The experimental results in Barrett and Dannenberg (2012) support the hypothesis of failure to avoid impacts under thresholds uncertainty. As shown in figure 2, in nearly all games played in either threshold uncertainty or threshold and impact uncertainty, the players did not commit enough resources to avoid catastrophes.

While the stronger hypothesis of zero group contribution under uncertainty did not hold, results show that average group contribution about halved. The experiment showed the breakdown of cooperation under threshold and dual uncertainty. The follow-up questionnaires reveal that participants are risk averse, but this has no effect on behavior. Barrett and Dannenberg conclude that behavior is more shaped by the context of the game than by individual preferences.

An interesting observation is that goals change when acting under threshold uncertainty. To open-ended questions participants in the certainty and impact uncertainty game overwhelmingly answered "joint payoff maximization,

Figure 2: The probability of catastrophe avoidance under scenarios involving certainty, impact uncertainty, threshold uncertainty and dual uncertainty. The threshold was crossed and catastrophe occurred in nearly all groups. (Barrett and Dannenberg (2012), p. 17373)

signaling of intended contribution/creation of trust, and fair share to reach target/compensation of potentially missing contributions” as most important reasons. In threshold and dual uncertainty, the reasons explained by the majority of participants change to “stimulation of others’ contributions/realistic target, own payoff maximization, resignation/distrust, compromise between group and own interest” (Barrett and Dannenberg (2012), Supplementary Information Table S6).

The model in Barrett (2013) suggests different types of games being played for the cases of threshold certainty or uncertainty. The results of the mathematical modeling show, that threshold uncertainty increases the minimum value of the impact level which countries would be willing to acquiesce. For a known threshold, e.g. 600, the minimum value of impact to force cooperation to eliminate chance of catastrophe would be 50, while in a coordination environment the minimum impact level would be 421. In this case the catastrophe avoidance is both collectively optimal and a symmetric Nash equilibrium, hence a coordination game. The values here are nominal, without any relation to a physical variable. For the slight uncertainty of a threshold in the range from 590 to 610, the minimum impact level to force cooperation would rise to 55, while in the coordination environment it would rise to 8703, a twenty-fold increase (Barrett, 2013). The increase changes the payout matrix, and avoiding catastrophe is still the collectively optimal outcome, but not a Nash equilibrium, hence a prisoners dilemma. As shown in figure 3, the mathematical model developed by Barrett enables the evaluation of threshold uncertainty on the nature of the game. If the payout-function is known, it is possible to infer the game being played or any

combination of threshold and impacts. The model shows the comparably drastic differences in accepted impact level when acting under either cooperation or coordination, and when acting under either threshold certainty or uncertainty.

Figure 3: For any combination of impact X and threshold \bar{Q} it is possible to say whether it is a coordination game, a cooperation game, or a situation where avoiding catastrophe is inefficient.

In the situation where the threshold is known, there are huge disincentives for free-riding behavior. When the threshold is uncertain, there are only tiny disincentives for deviation from the collectively optimal solution, and ones free-riding behavior is not expected to lead to catastrophe. In other words: with certain thresholds cooperation is self-enforcing, with uncertain thresholds cooperation breaks down.

3 Critique of assumptions

3.1 Characteristics

The main characteristic of Barrett's approach to climate policy is the use of game theory. The second most important aspect is his special focus on threshold uncertainty. With the help of a mathematical model and an experiment Barrett aims to show that there is a distinction between climate impact and impact thresholds, a distinction that is important to make when trying to improve the decision making processes involved in climate policy.

Barrett translates the global community of countries into a collection of players, which have the options of cooperating or not. The choices available range from inaction over cooperation to coordination, and enable strategic behaviour like free-riding. Players receive incentives in form of payouts, which differ for different individual and collective choices.

The situation Barrett constructs is indeed applicable to more situations than climate change. Any situation involving an unknown threshold can be reframed and analyzed with this model. Examples named include debris space, clogging an orbit beyond an unknown density and making it unusable; the development of antibiotic resistance of pathogens, beyond an uncertain level of drug use; and the over-exploitation of renewable resources like fish, beyond an uncertain lower boundary of extraction.

These situations are not only described by involving threshold uncertainty? Other characteristics of these situations are externalities, and that they concern an open access resource or commons. The fundamental problem of an open access resource is overuse, resulting in collapse of the resource. The problem gets intensified when the threshold of collapse is not known or uncertain, creating further disincentives for cautionary behavior and reduction of use.

Here arises one issue in respect to climate change. While tackling climate change is often framed as a prisoners dilemma game, it is not clear whether threshold uncertainty really is at the core of the problem. While it is true that the breakdown of cooperation is the reason for inaction, the reasons may not be mainly threshold uncertainty but strategic behaviour by the actors. Free-riding on other actors contributions is one alternative explanation, another one is that tackling climate change is seen as inefficient.

3.2 Methodological Issues

This section extracts and reviews the basic assumption of Barretts approach to climate change policy. Three issues are raised here. The first one is the assumption of homogeneous actors. The second one concerns the game theoretic assumptions about the structure of the payout matrix. The third one concerns the fundamental assumption of scientific uncertainty about climate change thresholds.

Player homogeneity. In the experiment as well as the mathematical model, players are homogeneous. That means every player has the same benefit function and payout matrix. The homogeneity of actors may facilitate modeling and lead to distinct results. Regarding climate change policy the homogeneity of actors (representing countries) may be an improper assumption. There are various cases that deviate from this assumption:

1. Countries benefit differently from cooperation. This distinction may be exemplified by comparing a small island country with a large landlocked country in a temperate climate zone. The small island country may be very inclined to cooperate since benefits are high, the large landlocked country may be less inclined to cooperate since benefits are relatively small.
2. Countries have different cost functions for avoiding catastrophes. Higher mitigation costs in e.g. transitional economies with high growth and a fossil fuel based energy infrastructure, need higher benefits of avoiding catastrophe compared to service-based, renewable energy based economy.

Game situation classification. There exists a range of games with different configurations of equilibria (see [Holzinger \(2003\)](#)). A game's payout matrix is analyzed by number of Nash equilibria (zero, one, multiple) on one hand, and by Pareto-efficiency of a payoff on the other hand. The situations described by Barrett are assurance games for the case of coordination, and asymmetric dilemma games for the case of cooperation. An assurance game is characterized by having multiple Nash equilibria, which may or may not be Pareto-optimal ([Holzinger \(2003\)](#)). Joint gains may be maximized in the optimal equilibrium, but there is a risk this may not be achieved. Asymmetric dilemmas are characterized by having one Nash equilibrium, which is a Pareto-inefficient outcome. The Pareto-optimal result is not achieved because the situation is strongly unequal. There arises not only a cooperation problem like in the prisoners dilemma, but a distributional problem as well. Since gains within the Pareto-optimal situation are distributed very differently, players need a contract to redistribute them. This applies to the climate change problem in the way that countries look at the net benefits of impact avoidance, and how they are distributed. While different games may be played temporarily, in the longterm climate change always regresses to a prisoners dilemma game, since no higher authority may impose sanctions to remove the Pareto-inefficient outcome from each player's strategies.

Scientific threshold uncertainty. Climate science is a highly complex endeavor, and there exist multiple causes for uncertainty about its statements. One group of causes lies on the side of physical climate science, the other group of causes lies on the side of climate models and economic climate modeling. Physical climate science can make statements with high levels of confidence for most cases of drivers and impacts. One notable exception is the role of clouds in the weather cycle (see [IPCC \(2013\)](#) p. 14). Climate models and especially models of economic impacts are much more uncertain. On the one hand due to the complexity of mathematical modeling and high computational requirements, on the other hand due to lack of understanding of interaction between climate and socioeconomic systems on any resolution lower than global. The uncertainties communicated along with the model results usually leave room for interpretation by policy makers and, as Barrett and Dannenberg have shown, lead to risk taking beyond what is collectively optimal.

The question arises whether it is possible to reduce threshold uncertainty, e.g. by establishing an upper or lower bound, or by significantly narrowing the band. [Knutti and Sedlacek \(2012\)](#) show that the robustness of climate model projections increases, but convergence of models is slow. Knutti's and Sedlacek's comparison of temperature and precipitation models shows quite high agreement between temperature models, but only medium agreement between precipitation models. Knutti and Sedlacek attribute the lack of convergence and therefore reduction of uncertainty to seven possible causes. (1) are limitations of computational resources and spatial resolution, (2) is a lack of process understanding, (3) is missing data in the form of accurate long term observations, (4) is a lack of consensus on metrics that enable evaluation of models, (5) is internal

variability of climate change limiting predictability, (6) is the introduction of dissimilar models, and (7) is the addition of new elements into climate models.

4 Conclusion

The main results of (Barrett and Dannenberg, 2012) and (Barrett, 2013) are that threshold uncertainty changes the nature of the game being played in climate change policy making to an assurance game or asymmetric dilemma. The arguments are underpinned by an experimental setup and a mathematical model. This review argues that while threshold uncertainty is a real problem in some situations, and Barrett makes valuable contributions here, but the link to climate change is weak. Issues here are the game theoretic assumptions (player homogeneity instead of heterogeneity) and classifications (prisoners dilemma instead of asymmetric dilemma with a distributional component), as well as the point of scientific threshold uncertainty, which may not be the size of a problem like Barrett argued. While there exist a range of collective action problems where threshold uncertainty may be at the heart of the problem, it does not as clearly apply to climate change.

In order to achieve a higher relevance regarding climate change and climate policy making, there are some possibilities to reframe the problem. One suggestion for further experiments are repeated games with positive or negative external reinforcement, which represent climate externalities. Those games should not be designed about social enforcement of rules (that won't be applicable to global problems soon), but about direct causal feedback from ones action to ones payout. Repeated games are also better applicable to climate negotiations, which happen regularly and involve updating of information (payout matrices) available to actors.

A further interesting link that should be explored, is the relation of threshold uncertainty with commons. The handling of threshold uncertainty in a commons framework, where resources are open-access but rivalled, may be an area for research. Are there examples where commons are threatened by threshold uncertainty, or are there examples where the problem of threshold uncertainty has been solved, and how?

Implications for Policy Making Barrett's results have three implications for climate policy making. The first implication is, that a target like 2°C maximum warming is not going to achieve enough commitment under the current framework. The second one arises out of the irreducibility of threshold uncertainty, and implies that it is not possible to change the game situation for all players. The third implication is a consequence of the first and second one, that for the highly probable case that the institutional setting cannot be adapted adequately, a climate catastrophe may not be avoided, and policy making has to shift to damage reduction and adaptation.

Targets may not be reached within the current institutional setting for two reasons. As long as enforcement is not possible, free-riding behavior will occur,

and as long as ignorance of common goals out of self-interest is not going to have adverse effects, defection will happen. The key issue here is lack of (credible) enforcement by a superior authority, which in the case of nation states as players, does not exist.

Threshold uncertainty may be reduced, but as e.g. Knutti and Sedlacek have shown, this may take a long time. The climate is a very complex system, and even empirical evidence in the form of severe weather events, is difficult to attribute and does not help in determining the threshold. There remains considerable residual uncertainty which is going to impede coordination and cooperation between a large set of countries. The key issue here is that countries differentiate in expected impacts, and some may be able to tolerate or risk higher thresholds, while others are vulnerable and need a lower threshold.

To solve the problem, Barrett repeatedly suggests trade restrictions and the adoption of technological standards with positive network externalities. The example used by Barrett, the successful implementation of the Montreal Protocol, is not completely appropriate. The Montreal Protocol banned the use of chlorofluorocarbons (CFC), a compound that could be easily be technologically substituted. Trade restrictions may act as an enforcement, but are politically not very feasible. The adoption of technological standards with positive network externalities may create a pull towards coordination, but technological development is not predictable, and a mere technological effect is not going to have enough impact on climate policy. The key issues here is how to incentivise cooperation in climate policy.

The best solution would be to create a supranational entity equipped with decision making capabilities, regulatory authority and financial and material resources to act or to redistribute. This entity would be mandated to develop and realize the globally best solution for climate change. This requires the transfer of sovereign power and resources, and is not going to happen in the near future. A second possible solution is to develop a mechanism of how to share not only the burden, but also gains of mitigation and adaptation.

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References

- Barrett, S. (2013). Climate treaties and approaching catastrophes. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 66(2):235–250.
- Barrett, S. and Dannenberg, A. (2012). Climate negotiations under scientific uncertainty: Supplementary Information. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(43):17372–17376.
- Holzinger, K. (2003). The Problems of Collective Action: A New Approach. *MPI Collective Goods Preprint*, (2003/2).

IPCC (2013). IPCC, 2013: Summary for Policymakers. In Stocker, Qin, Plattner, Tignor, Allen, Boschung, Nauels, Xia, Bex, and Midgley, editors, *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA.

Knutti, R. and Sedlacek, J. (2012). Robustness and uncertainties in the new CMIP5 climate model projections. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(4):369–373.